

Notes on the wolf spider *Hippasosa guttata* (Karsch, 1878) in South Africa (Araneae: Lycosidae)

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ABSTRACT: The wolf spider *Hippasosa guttata* (Karsch, 1878) was described as *Lycosa guttata* from Mozambique. It is presently known throughout Central and Southern Africa and more information is provided here on their morphology, distribution in South Africa, and interesting burrow-dwelling behaviour with images of live specimens.

Key words: biodiversity, burrow dweller, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Hippasosa* Roewer, 1960 is represented by 13 species, of which eight are known from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog 2022). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), a large number of Lycosidae specimens were sampled. One of the species was identified as *Hippasosa guttata* (Karsch, 1878). The species was described as *Lycosa guttata* from Mozambique in 1878. It was listed for several years as *Ocyale guttata* (Alderweireldt, 1996) and was only recently transferred to *Hippasosa* (Sherwood, 2022). It has been recorded throughout Central and Southern Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

Species of *Hippasosa* are among the larger wolf spiders and colour wise are remarkable wolf spiders. Despite these features, little is known about their biology. The only record on their burrowing behaviour was by Jocqué *et al.* (2017) of *H. ghost* (Jocqué & Jocqué, 2017) in Madagascar.

In this paper the general morphology and burrow-living behaviour of *H. guttata* are discussed and illustrated with photographs of live specimens.

METHODS

The photographs of the species in the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) provided important information on morphology and behaviour. The striking differences between preserved and living specimens stress the importance of documenting live patterns and colours in species descriptions as colours usually fade when specimens are fixed in ethanol. Voucher specimens collected during the SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

TAXONOMY

Hippasosa guttata (Karsch, 1878)

Lycosa guttata Karsch, 1878: 329.

Trochosa guttata Pavesi, 1881: 552.

Crocodilosa guttata Roewer, 1960: 850.

Ocyale guttata Alderweireldt, 1996: 1356, Jocqué *et al.*, 2017; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021. (*Ocyale* was declared a nomen dubium (in Pisauridae) by Sherwood (2022).

Hippasosa guttata Sherwood, 2022: 583.

Descriptive characteristics: Female: total length 15–20 mm. Carapace pale brown with paler lateral margins and irregular central markings (Fig. 1). Sternum yellow; clypeus pale yellow; chelicerae pale brown; palp pale brown. Abdomen dorsally greyish with two diverging rows of paler spots, pattern variable (Fig. 2); ventrally pale grey.

Figs 1–3. *Hippasosa guttata* females. Photos: 1. Piet van Dyk. 2–3. Peter Webb.

Figs 4–8. *Hippasosa guttata*: 4. Female's ventral view. 5. Carapace dorsal view. 6. Epigyne. 7. Line drawing male palp. 8. Line drawing epigyne. Photos: 4–6. A. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 7–8. After Alderweireldt (1996).

Legs: Yellow to brown banded (Fig. 3); tibia I ventrally with two pairs of spines and one additional apical pair. Epigyne: Longitudinal pair of inverted T slender and usually as long as transverse part (Figs 6 & 8); lateral margins along median septum well developed, swollen, and shiny. Male: Total length 15–17 mm. Carapace: Darker than female, brown with paler lateral margins and irregular paler central band (Fig. 15). Sternum yellow, somewhat darkened towards edges. Clypeus pale brown; chelicerae brown. Abdomen dorsal surface grey with two rows of white spots, ventral surface pale grey. Legs: Pale brown with darker annulations; tibia I with two pairs of ventral spines and one apical pair. Palp: Pale brown, tarsus somewhat darker (Fig. 7).

HABITAT

The species was sampled from the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) biomes. It was also sampled from agri-ecosystems (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023).

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-running ground dwellers and were frequently sampled from pitfall traps. They are very well camouflaged and blend in with their surroundings (Fig. 15) (Webb, 2014). Little is known about their general behaviour.

The first observations on their burrow-dwelling behaviour were made while sampling at Ezemvelo Nature Reserve in Gauteng. The second author found a spider burrow, about 9 mm across, lined with silk (Fig. 11) one late evening. As there was no spider visible, he decided to examine the burrow in the morning. However, the next morning no traces of the burrow could be found. After scanning the area he did eventually find the burrow (Fig. 10). It was closed over with a soft silk flap, well camouflaged with sand particles (Fig. 9). The flap was a floppy extension of the tunnel itself and when open it forms a rim around the burrow entrance on the ground (Fig. 12). To close the entrance, the spider lifts the flap and pulls it towards the centre, forming a sand-covered soft trapdoor. The burrow entrance remained closed during the day, but in the evening, it was open, and the spider was observed sitting in the entrance (Fig. 12) and seen leaving the burrow (Fig. 13).

Figs 9–14. Burrow of *Hippasosa guttata* as observed at the Ezemvelo Nature Reserve. Photos: Peter Webb.

Fig. 15. *Hippasosa guttata* blending in with surroundings. Photo: Piet Grobler.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Hippasosa guttata is known from eight African countries: Botswana, Mozambique, Namibia, Rwanda, Tanzania, Zambia, Zimbabwe, and South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2022). In South Africa, it is known from four provinces: KwaZulu-Natal, Mpumalanga, Gauteng, and Limpopo (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010).

CONSERVATION

The species has a wide global distribution. In South Africa it is sampled from seven protected areas with two published surveys: Kruger National Park (Robertson *et al.*, 2011) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Gauteng: Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (Crocodile Farm) (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Scottburgh (-30.28, 30.75); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6181, 32.2294); Umseleni (-28.33, 31.08). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Klein Letaba (-23.13, 30.43); Wood-bush Forest Reserve (-23.78, 30.07); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Vhembe Biosphere Gonden (Communal land)(-24.905, 29.994); Vyeboom (-24.77, 28.47). **mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park: Skukuza (-24.99, 31.59); Kruger National Park: Skukuza-Malelane (-25.109, 31.624).

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